

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

MANAGEMENT OF QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF TEACHING AND METHODOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF A TEACHER OF A MILITARY, SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract

In modern conditions, the competitiveness of a military, special educational institution in the educational market is determined by the quality of the provision of educational services and the economic efficiency of activities. Improving the quality of educational services of a military, special educational institution is an urgent socially and economically significant problem. The article shows a possible system for the formation of the competitiveness of a military, special educational institution through an assessment of the quality of the educational process, the problem of the transition of a military, special educational institution to digital support of indicative monitoring of the quality of services provided is raised. Quality monitoring is presented in the form of a program or information system, the work of which is carried out in a military, special educational institution through highlighted interrelated elements. A result-oriented model of management and assessment of the quality of work of a military, special educational institution is proposed. The indicative indicators for assessing the quality of the teaching and methodological activity of the teacher are considered and described. The publication was prepared as part of an applied grant research for 2020-2022. by order of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the topic "Development of a comprehensive methodology for assessing the quality of education of graduates of military special educational institutions.

Keywords: Quality assessment, indicative indicators, monitoring program, educational and methodological activities, professional activities, result.

Economy The Republic of Kazakhstan switched to market relations, in light of which higher professional education, including military education, found itself in fundamentally new conditions of functioning, which led to some difficulties. This is due to the fact that it realizes not only the function of reproducing highly qualified professional military personnel and other social mobility, such as building up the intellectual potential of the army and society, spreading the most socially significant cultural norms of preserving, increasing and continuity between generations of the best social values.

The high social significance of the military educational services market makes this market socially oriented, where competition mechanisms play a subordinate role. The functioning of the system of higher professional military education in Kazakhstan is closely linked and is largely determined by the pace and level of economic reform. The growing share of immaterial intellectually creative spiritual components provides a basis for a more specific analysis and study of the educational services market.

The increasing competition in the market of educational services orients a higher, specialized educational institution to build management based on the rational use of economic and intellectual resources. The task of higher, special educational institutions is not only to provide society with high-quality educational services in the field of higher military vocational education, but also their effective organization.

Assessment of the quality of education and its indicative indicators are currently one of the most pressing problems for the entire education system of the Republic of Kazakhstan. In 2017, the digital revolution entered a decisive phase - every second inhabitant of the Earth connected to the Internet. According to the McKinsey Global Institute (MGI), in the next 20 years, up to 50% of the world's work operations can be automated, and the scale of this process will be comparable to the industrial revolution of the 18th-19th centuries [1].

Digitalization is changing the face and structure of the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan, has a direct impact on the system of higher professional education. Intra-industry competition is growing, markets are expanding, competitiveness is increasing [2]. The digital economy is breaking the traditional patterns of industry markets. It increases the competitiveness of their members. Thus, digitalization determines the prospects for the growth of the education system, including in special educational institutions (hereinafter referred to as higher educational institutions).

Digital transformations are gradually entering the system of special educational institutions, but there are certain problems, this is especially noticeable in the lack of digital platforms that provide automated programs for monitoring the activities of the teaching staff and its assessment of the quality of professional activities [3].

A digital approach and an automated monitoring program should accurately show all stages of the professional activity of the teaching staff of a military specialized educational institution (MSEI), including design and prototyping, its maintenance, monitoring and optimization of monitoring, as well as data obtained as a result of feedback from participants included in this system. The industrialization of the educational process radically changes not only the pedagogical process, but also other spheres of professional activity (didactic, educational, methodological, scientific, research, educational) associated with the introduction of didactic innovations. Cyberphysical systems for building the activities of higher educational institutions will fundamentally change the traditional logic of building the educational process, since each of its participants (who has access to change the automated monitoring program) will determine what initial task must be completed to improve the quality of education and train highly qualified specialists [4]. This completely new architecture for building a monitoring system for an APU can be implemented gradually through digital modernization.

To do this, it is worth turning to the theories of quality management of the educational process in the higher educational institution, which allow us to identify objective regularities and understand the mechanism of management by determining the cause-and-effect relationships that affect the final result of the functioning and development of the higher educational institution. Of course, many indicators of the quality of the educational process are only an indicator of its functioning and development and by itself does not determine the content and direction of control actions. The determining factor is information on the numerical values of quality indicators and the degree of their influence on the educational process [5].

This circumstance makes it necessary to measure and assess the quality of the educational process using an automated quality assessment monitoring program.

The basis for the development of a methodology for assessing the quality of the educational process of higher educational institutions was the development of Kazakhstani and Russian scientists. In accordance with their recommendations within the framework of the project, the consideration of the educational process is based on the representation of this process as a system of functioning which is described by qualimetric and economic models [6]. Qualimetry is used for the economic assessment of both the quality of the entire educational process as a whole and the quality of the implementation of the main processes of professional activity of the teaching staff, which form the competitiveness of both the teacher and the student, as well as the higher educational institution itself. The determination of the numerical base values of indicators of the level of education quality is carried out by the methods of qualimetry.

The use of the qualimetric approach in assessing the quality of the educational process allows us to solve the methodological problem of standardizing research and the dimensions of the presentation of the studied indicators, which consists in the fact that the economic indicators of the educational process are expressed in monetary units, while the qualimetric indicators characterizing the quality of the educational process are usually expressed in dimensionless form.

To consider the problem posed, we use statistical, sociological and didactic methods that allow us to show indicative indicators for assessing the quality of the educational process, identify the elements of interest to us and create an information platform for quality management of the work of the higher educational institution oriented towards results. The adopted methodology for assessing the quality of the educational process is presented in the form of a system of indicators for the analytical assessment of the quality of the educational process. The sequence of assessing the quality of the educational process and the level of competitiveness has been determined (Figure 1).

Drawing 1

Result oriented model of management and quality assessment of higher specialized educational institutions

For the practical application of the automated monitoring program, which is the main composite indicator of the educational process in the higher educational institution, a system of indicators for analytical quality assessment has been developed, shown in (Table 1).

The system of indicators for assessing the quality of educational and methodological activities of the teaching staff makes it possible to assess the quality of

compliance of educational and methodological activities with the requirements of the Higher Education Institution, the educational standard and the customer represented by the Border Service of the National Security Committee of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

To do this, we propose to determine the indicators of educational and methodological activities of the teaching staff of the Higher Education Institution as the main professional activity, which is an element of the model of an automated monitoring program.

Table 1

The system of indicators for assessing the quality of educational and methodological activities of the teaching staff

indicators	formula
Indicators of working out of the EMC (educational and methodical complex)	$EMC = \frac{N1}{N2}$ where: N1- number of positions to fill N2- the level of education of the graduate in the discipline
Indicators of working out WC (working curriculum)	$WC = \frac{N1}{Nc}$ where: N1- number of positions to fill Nc- number of competencies developed
TP performance indicators (thematic plan)	$TP = \frac{Nc}{Ns}$ where: Nc- number of competencies developed Ns- number of training sessions (lectures, group classes, practical classes, seminars, complex classes, polyform)
Indicators of working out of CC (current control)	$CC = \frac{nt}{Ua+Ht}$ where: nt- number of trainees Ua- the level of achievement Ht- changing number of tasks (questions, tests)
Indicators of development of BC (boundary control)	$BC = \frac{nt}{Ua+Ht} * Nc$ where: nt- number of trainees Ua- the level of achievement Ht- changing number of tasks (questions, tests) Nc- number of competencies developed
The rate of mining e-magazine	$EM = \frac{nt * No}{Nr * Ur}$ where: nt- number of trainees No- number of outposts Nr- number of ratings to be issued Ur- level of knowledge acquisition in the discipline (rating)
Performance indicators of advanced training courses	$TC = \frac{Nc+Ncp}{Nh} / Ua$ where: Nc- number of certificates Ncp- number of certificates for the profile of the discipline taught Nh- number of hours Ua- level of assimilation (assessment of the completed course)
Performance indicators MSC (military science circle)	$MSC = \frac{Nlt+Ula+Nm}{ns}$ where: ns- the number of students Nlt- number of lesson topics Ula- the level of achievement (score on defense) Nm- number of prepared materials (articles, abstracts, theses, presentations)
Indicators of educational work	$EW = \frac{ns}{Nto} / Nea$ where: ns- the number of students Nto- number of training outposts Nea- number of educational activities carried out

The indicators and formulas given in the table include the following:

Educational-methodical complex The quality of training the educational-methodical complex directly depends on how competently, systematically and clearly the educational material on the discipline will be transferred. Since the EMC is a visual guide that helps to understand the academic discipline and understand the requirements for working out the materials put forward by the teacher. Based on this, it can be argued that the level of education of the student in the discipline directly depends on the educational and methodological complex of the discipline.

Working curriculum The working curriculum is a document that prescribes the leading goal and main objectives that the taught discipline strives to achieve, this document is based on the graduate's model and determines what competencies the student will develop in obtaining professional knowledge on the subject of the discipline.

Thematic plan is a document showing in detail the topics of the taught discipline and determining the depth of the formed competencies of the students.

Current control is an indicator of mastering knowledge in a discipline on a specific topic.

Midterm control is an indicator of mastering knowledge in a discipline for certain topics that develop a set of competencies for students.

The electronic journal is an automated service that allows participants in the educational process to reduce the administrative burden and receive timely access to information about current and midterm assessments.

Advanced training courses for the teaching staff is a mandatory position that shows how much the teacher strives to improve his professional knowledge and self-development.

The military scientific circle is the teacher's activity associated with the introduction of cadets into research activities, which is accompanied by educational and methodological work of the teacher and the preparation of cadets for the defense of term papers, speeches at conferences, round tables.

Educational work is the activity of a teacher associated with raising the cultural self-awareness of cadets, teachers, in accordance with the taught discipline, plan the topics of educational work.

The scientific goal of systematizing the indicators of educational and methodological activities of a teacher is to standardize the use of qualimetric and economic indicators to create a real, working automated program for monitoring the educational process in the higher educational institution.

Indicators of the quality of educational and methodological activities of a teacher characterize the degree of compliance of the content of the educational process with the requirements of the State Educational

Standard of Education, the customer, as well as the regulatory documents of the educational institution that determine the economic social and production components of the directly specified indicators of the educational process. Taken together, the indicators describe the impact of educational and methodological activities on the educational process of the higher educational institution.

These indicators characterize the system of an automated program for monitoring the educational process in the higher educational institution, as well as to what extent the teaching and methodological activities of the teacher can use the capabilities of the developed program.

The developed program for monitoring the educational process can be used in assessing and shaping the competitiveness of higher educational institutions. When analyzing qualimetric indicators, it is possible to establish the degree of fulfillment by cadets and teachers of the requirements imposed by regulatory requirements and documents for the educational process, as well as the quality of the monitoring program itself.

The proposed program for monitoring the educational process allows us to consider the indicative qualities and indicators of the educational and methodological activity of the teacher, which reveals the promising opportunities for the development of higher educational institutions and the assessment of the quality of the educational process.

The program contains elements of mobility that allow you to reconstruct the internal content of the program to meet the new requirements that arise in the light of the development and improvement of the educational process and indicative assessment of its quality. It can be supplemented with elements that are theoretically substantiated and have indicative components capable of monitoring professional activities, identifying problematic aspects and pointing out them.

References:

1. www.inbusiness.kz
2. www.kazportal.kz
3. Kaldybaev S. K., Beishenaliev A. B. the Quality of the educational process in the structure of the quality of education. - 2015. - No. 7. - Pp. 90-97.
4. Soros Foundation-Kazakhstan «Educational policy: dialogue with society». Discussion paper «Applied research in the field of educational policy», Almaty, 2002.
- 5 The world conference on higher education: Framework for action. - <http://www.unesco.org/Education/Webmaster>.
6. Kiss V. Quality Assurance in Tertiary Education: Current Practices in OECD Countries and Literary Review on Potential Effects. 2005.